

Selective recognition of Zn²⁺ by a triazole linked thiophene-methylimine based derivative of calix[6]arene and the secondary sensing of biothiols by the corresponding zinc complex[†]

Anita Nehra, Vijay Kumar Hinge, Rahul Nag and Chebrolu Pulla Rao*

Bioinorganic Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Powai, Mumbai-400 076, India

E-mail: cp Rao@iitb.ac.in

Manuscript received online 01 November 2018, accepted 22 November 2018

A 1,3,5-tris-triazole linked thiophene-methylimino appended calix[6]arene conjugate, **L** has been shown to bind to Zn²⁺ selectively in ethanol among the metal ions studied which include, alkali and alkaline earth ions, transition metal ions and lanthanides by fluorescence, absorption and ESI-MS. The conjugate, **L** exhibited ~25 fold increase in its fluorescence intensity at $\lambda_{em} = 450$ nm in presence of Zn²⁺ upon exciting at 330 nm with a limit of detection of 25 ± 4 ppb while the K_a is $(2.31 \pm 0.1) \times 10^5$ M⁻¹. The control molecules, **C**₁ and **C**₂ which lack iminophenolic core and calix[6]arene platform respectively have been studied. These do not show considerable changes in their fluorescence emission in presence of Zn²⁺ implying the essential role of both the arene cavity as well as the role of the three arms to bind to Zn²⁺. Absorption studies further support the binding of Zn²⁺ to **L** by exhibiting isosbestic points at 294 and 344 nm and stoichiometry of the 1:1 complex formed between **L** and Zn²⁺ was confirmed by ESI-MS. The computationally optimized structure of {**L**+Zn²⁺} complex exhibited distorted octahedral geometry about Zn²⁺ with N₃O₃ core. The *in situ* generated complex, {**L**+Zn²⁺} interacts with biologically relevant thiols by exhibiting fluorescence quenching of the complex due to the release of Zn²⁺ from its complex which is further supported by absorption and ESI-MS studies.

Keywords: Selective sensor for Zn²⁺, fluorescence enhancement, ternary species, iminophenolic core, 1,3,5-tris-derivative of calix[6]arene, triazole linked calix[6] conjugate.

Introduction

By beginning of this century, calixarenes are well known to be potential supramolecular systems. These are amenable for functionalization with suitable binding as well as reporter groups essentially to act as good hosts and also as selective sensors for various ions and molecules through their flexible arms built at either lower- or upper rim or at both¹⁻⁴. In biological systems, Zn²⁺ is one of the most abundant transition metal ions and plays important roles⁵ in cellular physiology⁶⁻¹¹. It is well established that Zn²⁺ exists in the form of labile ion pools in the organs, such as, pancreas, prostate and brain¹²⁻¹⁸ and its deficiency causes various disorders such as Parkinson's disease, epilepsy and certain type of cancers¹⁹⁻²⁴. Moreover, Zn²⁺ is also associated with cysteine rich metallothioneins during heavy metal detoxification and the oxidative stress²⁵⁻²⁹. Therefore, the development of synthetic receptors for the selective recognition of Zn²⁺ by fluores-

cence is of great interest to chemists due the enhanced sensitivity of this technique. Several fluorescent probes have been reported in the literature for Zn²⁺ based on small molecular systems as well as calixarenes³⁰⁻³⁵. The contributions made by our group in case of Zn²⁺ on the basis of calix[4,6]arene conjugates are noteworthy³⁶⁻³⁸. In this paper, we report the synthesis, characterization and metal ion binding studies of triazole linked thiophene-methylimine based derivative of calix[6]arene, **L** by fluorescence, absorption and ESI-MS spectroscopy. The secondary sensing of **L** towards thiols has been demonstrated and all the results were pooled in order to design an INHIBIT logic gate.

Experimental

Materials and methods: All the metal salts (used as their perchlorates) and the thiols used in this paper were procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Reagent grade chloroform and ethanol

[†]Professor A. S. R. Anjaneyulu 60th Birthday Commemoration Lecture (2017).

were used in the present studies. NMR spectra were measured on Bruker NMR spectrometer (500 MHz or 400 MHz) and ESI-MS spectra on maXis Impact High Resolution Mass Spectrometer (Bruker). Absorption and emission spectra were measured on UV 2101-PC UV-VIS Scanning Spectrophotometer and LS55 Fluorescence Spectrometer respectively.

Synthesis and characterization of L: Compound **P₃** (Scheme 1, 1.00 g, 0.546 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (20 mL) by heating to which thiophene-methyl amine (0.18 g, 0.16 mmol) was added and stirred the mixture for 12 h at RT. After 12 h, yellow colored precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed with methanol for 4–5 times and the precipitate was dried under vacuum. Yield (0.7 g, 62%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 0.7 (s, 27H, sal-C(CH₃)₃), 1.2 (s, 27H, C(CH₃)₃), 1.3 (s, 27H, C(CH₃)₃), 2.1 (s, 9H, OCH₃), 3.3 (d, 6H, Ar-CH₂_{eq}-Ar, *J* 15.08), 4.5 (d, 6H, Ar-CH₂_{ax}-Ar, *J* 15.24), 4.9 (s, 6H, Ar-CH₂), 5.0 (s, 6H, OCH₂), 5.5 (s, 6H, OCH₂), 6.6 (s, 6H, Ar-H), 6.9 (s, 6H, Ar-H), 7.2 (s, 3H, Ar-H), 7.3 (s, 3H, Ar-H), 7.9 (s, 3H, Ar-H), 8.3 (s, 3H, imine-H), 13.6 (s, 3H, sal-OH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 29.9 (Ar-CH₂-Ar), 31.3, 31.4, 31.5 (-C(CH₃)₃), 34.1, 34.1, 34.4 (-C(CH₃)₃), 49.0 (thiazole-CH₂), 57.0, 60.2 (-O-CH₃), 66.7 (thiophene-CH₂), 76.88 (-O-CH₂), 118.3, 122.1, 123.7, 123.8, 125.9, 127.3, 128.2, 129.2, 130.9, 133.1, 133.7, 140.5, 141.7, 144.8, 145.8, 146.0, 151.8, 154.6, 157.1 (Ar-C, thiophene-C), 165.9 (-NH=C). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃₁H₁₆₄N₁₂O₁₁S₃·2CH₃OH: Calcd.: C, 72.21; H, 7.59; N, 7.71%. Found: C, 72.11; H, 7.40; N, 7.66%; HR-MS for C₁₂₉H₁₅₇N₁₂O₉S₃, [M+H]⁺ Calcd. 2114.1359, Found 2114.1467; FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 1634 (ν_{C=N}), 3442 (ν_{OH}).

Synthesis and characterization of C₁: Compound **P₁** (Scheme 1, 0.1 g, 0.08 mmol) and benzylazide (0.15 g, 1.18 mmol) were dissolved in 20 mL of dichloromethane, *tert*-butanol and water in a mixture of volume ratio as 1:1:2. To this, CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.03 g, 1.15 mmol) and sodium ascorbate (0.05 g, 0.23 mmol) were added and the solution was stirred for 12 h at RT. Upon completion of the reaction as checked by TLC, the organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (2×50 mL). The combined organic layer was washed with brine (2×50 mL), dried over Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was removed under the reduced pressure and the hexane was added to provide pure white colored product (Yield 0.09 g, 64%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 0.79 (s, 27H, C(CH₃)₃), 1.35 (s, 27H, C(CH₃)₃),

2.1 (s, 9H, OCH₃), 3.31 (d, 6H, Ar-CH₂_{eq}-Ar, *J* 15.08), 4.5 (d, 6H, Ar-CH₂_{ax}-Ar, *J* 15.24), 5.06 (s, 6H, Ar-CH₂), 5.54 (s, 6H, OCH₂), 6.6 (s, 6H, Ar-H), 7.2 (s, 6H, Ar-H), 7.3 (s, 15H, Ar-H), 7.7 (s, 3H, triazole-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 29.92 (Ar-CH₂-Ar), 31.26, 31.38, 31.76, (-C(CH₃)₃), 34.13, 34.38 (-C(CH₃)₃), 54.32 (Ar-CH₂), 60.26 (O-CH₃), 66.72 (-O-CH₂), 123.09, 123.86, 128.06, 128.22, 128.84, 129.26, 133.05, 133.76, 134.82, 145.47, 145.98, 146.24, 151.53, 154.45 (Ar-C). Anal. Calcd. for C₉₉H₁₁₇N₉O₆: Calcd.: C, 77.76; H, 7.71; N, 8.24%. Found: C, 77.26; H, 7.9; N 8.1%.

Synthesis and characterization of C₂: The precursors, P₄ and P₅ (Scheme 1) have been synthesized by following the literature procedures³⁹. The synthesis of C₂ is same as that of L (0.45 g, yield 70%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ ppm): 1.3 (2s, 18H, C(CH₃)₃), 4.95 (s, 2H, thiophene-CH₂), 5.14 (s, 2H, NCH₂), 5.6 (s, 2H, -OCH₂), 6.9–7.3 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.4 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.85 (s, 1H, triazole-H), 8.4 (s, 1H, -C=NH), 13.6 (s, 1H, Ar-OH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 31.55, 31.70, 34.25, 49.10, 57.30, 62.36, 114.41, 118.39, 122.15, 123.64, 125.50, 125.91, 126.44, 127.30, 129.28, 131.15, 140.43, 141.93, 144.46, 156.30, 157.17, 165.99 (C=N); ESI MS *m/z*: 539.24 observed for [M+Na]⁺.

Details of fluorescence measurements: The metal ion recognition studies of L have been carried out using fluorescence spectroscopy in ethanol by exciting the solutions at 330 nm and measuring the emission in the range of 340–600 nm. Bulk solutions of L and the metal salts were prepared in ethanol by dissolving L initially in 50 μL of chloroform. All the fluorescence titrations were carried out in 1 cm quartz cells by maintaining the final [L] at 5 μM in a total volume of 3 mL achieved by diluting with ethanol and by varying the mole ratio of the added metal ion. The absorption titration studies were carried out using the same solutions.

Computational methodology: The initial model for L has been prepared from the crystal structures of the copper complex reported in the literature⁴⁰ upon bringing requisite modifications. In order to reduce the computational times, each *tert*-butyl group has been replaced by a hydrogen. The resultant structure has been optimized initially under PM3 and the output from this study has been given as input for the HF/3-21G level of calculations. The complex of L with Zn²⁺ was prepared by placing Zn²⁺ far away from the arms of L in such a way that the salicyl O- and imine N- are pointed towards Zn²⁺.

Results and discussion

Receptor (L) and control (C₁ and C₂) molecules: The receptor molecule **L** has been synthesized in four steps starting from *p*-*tert*-butylcalix[6]arene as per the steps given in Scheme 1^{41–44}. The **L** has been characterized using ¹H and ¹³C NMR, ESI-MS and elemental analysis. Details of the synthesis and characterization have been given in the Experimental Section.

The **L** exists in a flattened cone conformation as supported by NMR spectra. The **L** has a pre-organized N₃O₃ binding core formed by a Schiff's base -N and phenolic -O along with three thiophene 'S' centers. This conjugate is comparable with our previously reported derivative³⁹. The reported one having pyridyl moiety exhibiting N₆O₃ core has been shown to be selective for La³⁺³⁹. Therefore in order to see the effect of terminal moiety on the sensitivity of the iminophenolic core, the pyridyl moiety has been replaced by a thiophene moiety. Lanthanide ions being hard, these prefer to bind to 'O' and 'N' donor sites as compared to the soft 'S' sites. The lanthanides also demand higher coordination number. As a result of these two factors, the present conju-

gate, **L** possessing thiophene moiety exhibited favour for Zn²⁺ over that of the La³⁺. The interaction studies of **L** with 3d-transition, alkali, alkaline earth and lanthanide ions have been carried out using emission and absorption spectroscopy.

The control molecule, **C₁** has been prepared by cycloaddition reaction between tris-propargyl of calix[6]arene (**P₁**) and benzyl azide at room temperature in aqueous-*t*-BuOH (Scheme 1)⁴⁴. Single armed molecule, **C₂** has been synthesized in three steps starting from *p*-*tert*-butylphenol following the same synthesis strategy as shown for **L** on calix[6]arene platform (Scheme 1)³⁹.

Fluorescence titration studies of L with metal ions: The **L** exhibits very weak emission at 440 nm by exciting at 330 nm due to photo electron transfer (PET) of nitrogen lone pair of imine in ethanol. The metal ion recognition by **L** has been performed by screening several metal ions, viz. Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ag⁺, Hg²⁺, La³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, Eu³⁺, Gd³⁺, Dy³⁺, Ho³⁺ and Yb³⁺ in ethanol. When **L** has been titrated with Zn²⁺, a substantial fluorescence enhancement has been observed at 450 nm with a red shift of ~10 nm (Fig. 1a) with an increase

Scheme 1. Synthesis of **L** and the control molecules: (a) CuSO₄·5H₂O, sodium ascorbate, (*tert*-BuOH + dichloromethane (9:1)): water as 1:1 ratio, RT, 12 h; (b) thiophenemethyl amine, CH₃OH, RT, 12 h; (c) (azidomethyl)benzene, CuSO₄·5H₂O, sodium ascorbate, (*tert*-BuOH + dichloromethane (9:1)): water as 1:1 ratio, RT, 12 h; (d) propargyl bromide, potassium carbonate, dry acetone, reflux, 24 h; (e) 5-*tert*-butyl-3-(azidomethyl)-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, CuSO₄·5H₂O, sodium ascorbate, (*tert*-BuOH + dichloromethane (9:1)): water as 1:1 ratio, RT, 12 h; (f) thiophenemethyl amine, CH₃OH, RT, 12 h.

in intensity by ~25 fold (Fig. 1b). The enhancement is due to the chelation of Zn^{2+} that prevents PET. The association constant for **L** with Zn^{2+} is $(2.31 \pm 0.1) \times 10^5 M^{-1}$ based on the fluorescence data and this is derived using Benesi-Hildebrand equation⁴⁵. The minimum concentration of Zn^{2+} that can be detected by **L** is 25 ± 4 ppb ($0.39 \mu M$). Under the UV light, the solution of **L** is non-fluorescent whereas in the presence of Zn^{2+} it shows intense blue fluorescent color (Fig. 1b, inset). Metal ions such as Cd^{2+} and Mg^{2+} also exhibited increase in the emission intensity of **L** to a much lesser extent as compared to Zn^{2+} (Fig. 1c) whereas all other 22 metal ions studied showed no change in the fluorescence emission (Fig. 1c). Thus, **L** is highly sensitive and selective towards Zn^{2+} among all the metal ions studied.

Role of iminophenolic binding core for selective sensing

control molecules, viz. **C₁** and **C₂**. The **C₁** lacks iminophenolic core though the triazole moiety is present while the **C₂** has only single arm of **L** but without the calix[6]arene platform. **C₁** exhibits emission band at 310 nm upon exciting at 273 nm. When it is titrated with Zn^{2+} , no change is observed in its fluorescence emission indicating that iminophenolic core is essential to bind to Zn^{2+} as well as to show the blue emission (Fig. 2). On the other hand, the **C₂** exhibits emission band at 460 nm upon exciting at 326 nm. While **C₂** shows only ~5 fold increase in its fluorescence intensity at 460 nm when titrated with Zn^{2+} , this is ~5 times less than that of the **L**, suggesting that the calix[6]arene platform provides a pre-organized binding core for Zn^{2+} with three binding arms together to exhibit a collective emission enhancement and hence makes it an effective receptor for Zn^{2+} (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Fluorescence titration data: (a) spectral traces obtained during the titration of **L** with Zn^{2+} ; (b) relative fluorescence intensity ratio (I/I_0) as a function of $[Zn^{2+}]/[L]$; (c) histogram showing the relative fluorescence intensity ratio (I/I_0) as a function of metal ion.

of Zn^{2+} : In order to demonstrate the essential role of iminophenolic core as well as calix[6]arene platform, fluorescence studies have been carried out in ethanol with two

*Absorption studies of **L** with Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Cd^{2+} :* As fluorescence studies showed considerable to minimal changes only in case of Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Cd^{2+} , these metal

Fig. 2. Fluorescence titration of **L**, **C₁** and **C₂** with Zn^{2+} : (a) plot showing relative fluorescence intensity vs mole ratio; (b) histogram showing relative fluorescence intensity ratio (I/I_0) as a function of different molecules.

ions have been taken up for the absorption studies. The absorption spectrum of **L** exhibits bands at ~260 and ~325 nm. When incremental concentration of Zn²⁺ was added to **L**, the absorbance at ~325 nm decreases and a new band arises at 380 nm which exhibits increase in the absorbance up to one equivalent addition of Zn²⁺ (Fig. 3a). The isosbestic points observed at 294 and 344 nm clearly indicate the formation of the complex between **L** and Zn²⁺. When similar absorption titration of **L** has been carried out with Cd²⁺, the absorbance at 380 nm increases but no change was observed in case of 325 nm band. The absence of any clear cut isosbestic point suggests only weak interaction of Cd²⁺ with **L** (Fig. 3b). In presence of Mg²⁺, no considerable changes (Fig. 3c) have been observed in the absorption spectra of **L** indicating no significant binding.

that corresponds to [L+Zn⁺] and the isotopic peak pattern supports the presence of Zn²⁺ as the observed spectrum perfectly matches with that of the calculated one (Fig. 4).

Optimization of the species of sensing by computational studies: In order to provide the structural insight of the complex of **L** with Zn²⁺ formed during sensing, energy optimizations have been carried out with both **L** and its complex, {L+Zn²⁺} using Gaussian G03⁴⁶. In the optimized structure of the complex, the Zn²⁺ binds to three salicyaldimine oxygens and three imine nitrogens (Fig. 5a) resulting in six coordinated Zn²⁺ with distorted octahedral geometry while the sulphur of thiophene moiety stays far from the binding core with a Zn²⁺...S distance of ~5.5 Å (Fig. 5b).

Titration of {L+Zn²⁺} complex with thiols: Since the Zn²⁺ plays important role in the metal detoxification and oxidative

Fig. 3. Absorption titration of **L** with M²⁺: (a) spectral traces obtained during the titration of **L** with Zn²⁺. The Inset: absorbance vs [Zn²⁺]/[L] plots for bands at 325 and 380 nm; (b) and (c) are spectral traces for the titration of **L** with Cd²⁺ and Mg²⁺ respectively.

Species of sensing by ESI-MS: In order to find the species formed between **L** and Zn²⁺, ESI-MS studies were carried out. The ESI-MS spectrum obtained for the *in situ* generated complex results in a molecular ion peak at *m/z* = 2178

stress which are associated with cysteine rich proteins and metallothionein, the interaction of the complex has been studied with thiols. Therefore, the *in situ* generated complex, {L+Zn²⁺} has been further utilized to interact with Cys in-

Fig. 4. ESI mass spectral peak observed for {L + Zn²⁺} complex: (a) observed and (b) calculated.

Fig. 5. HF/LANL2DZ optimized structure of (a) **L**; (b) $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$ and the coordination sphere about the zinc ion. Bond lengths (Å) and bond angles ($^{\circ}$) in the coordination sphere are: $\text{Zn}-\text{O}_1 = 2.046$, $\text{Zn}-\text{O}_2 = 2.013$, $\text{Zn}-\text{O}_3 = 2.034$, $\text{Zn}-\text{N}_1 = 2.351$, $\text{Zn}-\text{N}_2 = 2.490$, $\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 2.273$. $\text{O}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_1 = 84$, $\text{O}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_2 = 86$, $\text{O}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 175$, $\text{O}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_2 = 105$, $\text{O}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_3 = 95$, $\text{N}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_2 = 95$, $\text{N}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 94$, $\text{N}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_2 = 85$, $\text{N}_1-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_3 = 178$, $\text{O}_3-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_2 = 83$, $\text{O}_3-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 87$, $\text{O}_3-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_2 = 97$, $\text{N}_2-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 90$, $\text{N}_2-\text{Zn}-\text{O}_2 = 168$, $\text{O}_2-\text{Zn}-\text{N}_3 = 79$.

cluding other biologically relevant thiol (-SH) containing molecules, such as, cysteine (Cys), dithiothreitol (DTT), glutathione reduced (GSH), homocysteine (Hcy) and cysteamine (Cyst). The interaction studies have been carried out using fluorescence, absorption and ESI-MS titrations.

Fluorescence titration of $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$ complex with thiols: The *in situ* generated complex, $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$ exhibits strong fluorescence emission at ~ 458 nm upon excitation at 325 nm. Upon incremental addition of Cys to this fluorescent complex, its emission intensity is quenched (Fig. 6a,b). Similar changes were observed in case of all other thiols studied except Cyst. The quenching is attributable to the removal of Zn^{2+} from its complex followed by chelation of the free Zn^{2+} by the thiols. At higher concentration (10 equiv.) of these thiols, the fluorescence spectra resemble that of simple **L**, supporting the release of Zn^{2+} from the complex. Cyst ex-

hibits enhancement due to the formation of a ternary complex, viz. $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}+\text{Cyst}\}$ (Fig. 6c). The quenching follows a trend among the thiols, i.e. $\text{Cys} \sim \text{GSH} > \text{DTT} \sim \text{Hcy}$ (Fig. 6c). Under UV light, the solution of the complex is non-fluorescent in presence of Cys and GSH, weakly fluorescent in presence of DTT and Hcy, and highly fluorescent in the presence of Cyst (Fig. 6c) which supports the emission result.

Absorption titrations of $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$ complex with thiols: In order to support the fluorescence titration results of the complex with thiols, additional studies were carried out by absorption spectroscopy. Upon titration of the complex with Cys, the absorbance of the band ~ 380 nm decreases and a new band at ~ 325 nm corresponding to the free receptor **L** regenerates as a function of the concentration of Cys (Fig. 7a). Other thiols also showed similar changes and the changes follow an order, viz. $\text{Cys} \sim \text{GSH} > \text{DTT} \sim \text{Hcy}$ (Fig. 7a-d).

Fig. 6. Fluorescence titration of $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$ with biologically relevant thiols: (a) spectral traces observed in case of the titration carried out using Cys; (b) plot of relative fluorescent intensity vs $[\text{thiol}]/[\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}]$; (c) histogram showing relative intensity for different thiols (10 equiv.) and the corresponding solutions. The photograph of the vials containing the following reaction mixture under 365 nm light illumination. Here C = $\{\mathbf{L}+\text{Zn}^{2+}\}$; 1 = C+Cys; 2 = C+GSH; 3 = C+DTT; 4 = C+Hcy and 5 = C+Cyst.

Therefore, the changes observed in case of all these thiols are attributable to the displacement of Zn^{2+} from the complex followed by release of free **L**. In contrast, Cyst exhibits increase in the absorbance at 380 nm which is similar to the fluorescence results and all this once again supports the stabilization of the complex by forming a ternary species, i.e. $\{L+Zn^{2+}+Cyst\}$ (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. (a) Absorption spectra obtained during the titration $\{L+Zn^{2+}\}$ complex with Cys (the inset shows plot of absorbance vs $[Cys]/[L+Zn^{2+}]$ for different bands). (b) Plot of absorbance vs $[thiol]/[L+Zn^{2+}]$ for different thiols at 380 nm band. (c) Histogram showing the highest absorbance of $\{L+Zn^{2+}\}$ when titrated with different thiols. (d) Absorption spectra obtained during the titration of $\{L+Zn^{2+}\}$ with different thiols.

ESI-MS titration of $\{L+Zn^{2+}\}$ complex with Cys and Cyst: In order to support the release of free **L**, ESI-MS studies of the complex treated with Cys has been carried out. When Cys is added to the complex, a peak is observed at $m/z = 2137$ that corresponds to free **L**, i.e. $[L+Na]$, while the peak corresponding to the complex disappears (Fig. 8a). However, in presence of Cyst, the complex peak at $m/z = 2178$ remains unchanged along with an additional peak at $m/z = 2280$ that corresponds to the ternary complex $\{[L+Zn^{2+}]+Cyst+Na\}$ which is in support of the observed fluorescence intensity increase due to the formation of the ternary species (Fig. 8b).

Conclusions and comparisons

A 1,3,5-tris-triazole linked thiophene-methyl imino appended calix[6]arene conjugate, **L** has been synthesized and characterized by analytical and spectral techniques. The conjugate, **L** possesses an iminophenolic binding motif on all the three arms of calix[6]arene resulting in the formation of a pre-organized core for metal ion binding. The binding studies were extended to alkali and alkaline earth, transition and lanthanide ions by fluorescence, absorption and ESI-MS. The **L** exhibited ~25 fold increase in its fluorescence intensity in presence of Zn^{2+} selectively among the metal ions studied upon exciting at 330 nm with a K_a of $(2.3 \pm 0.1) \times 10^5 M^{-1}$. The minimum detectable concentration of **L** is 25 ± 4 ppb. The role of the binding core as well as the calix[6]arene platform in Zn^{2+} binding has been delineated by performing similar fluorescence titrations with the control

Fig. 8. ESI-MS spectrum of $\{L+Zn^{2+}\}$ complex upon reacting with, (a) Cys and (b) Cyst.

molecules **C**₁ and **C**₂, which are devoid of iminophenolic core and calix[6]arene platform respectively. These control molecules do not show considerable changes in their fluorescence emission in presence of Zn²⁺ implying the essential role of both the arene cavity as well as calix-arms to bind to Zn²⁺. Absorption studies further supported the binding of Zn²⁺ to **L** by showing a decrease in the absorbance at ~325 nm and increase at 380 nm, and all this resulted in isosbestic points at 294 and 344 nm. The ESI-MS spectra showed 1:1 stoichiometry between **L** and Zn²⁺ and the observed isotopic peak pattern confirms the presence of Zn²⁺. The computationally optimized structure of {**L**+Zn²⁺} complex exhibited distorted octahedral geometry for the Zn²⁺ with N₃O₃ core. The *in situ* Zn²⁺-generated complex interacts with biologically relevant thiols by exhibiting fluorescence quenching due to the release of free **L** from its complex which has been further supported by absorption studies and confirmed by ESI-MS. In presence of Cys, ternary species have been formed which shows increase in the fluorescence as well as absorbance of the complex that is further confirmed by ESI-MS. The dual sensing of Zn²⁺ and Cys has also been demonstrated by INHIBIT molecular logic gate, wherein the zero refers to OFF state and one refers to the ON state, while the inputs are the presence of Zn²⁺ or Cys or both and the output is the intensity at 450 nm (*I*₄₅₀) as can be understood from Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. INHIBIT logic gate: Symbolic representation and table showing the response of **L** towards Zn²⁺ and Cys.

Acknowledgement

CPR thanks the SERB project and DST/SERB for JC Bose National Fellowship (SB/S2/JCB/066/2015) and IIT Bombay for Chair Professorship. AN acknowledges UGC for the fellowship. We acknowledge the services provided by the cen-

tral facilities of IIT Bombay.

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